

BOVINE LEUKOCYTE ADHESION DEFICIENCY SYNDROME (BLAD): A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Bovine leukocyte adhesion deficiency syndrome (BLAD) is an autosomal recessive hereditary disease in Holstein–Friesian cattle. The extensive use of artificial insemination led to the rapid spread of the condition during the 1990s worldwide. Irrespective of the introduction of genetic testing programs there are still carriers found among breeding animals. Therefore the problem needs to be popularized as rare but economically relevant that should be distinguished from other common causes for calthood maladies.

Key words: Bovine leukocyte adhesion deficiency, BLAD, Holstein–Friesian, autosomal recessive.

Introduction

About 70% of dairy cows are subjected to artificial insemination in order to produce higher yield per animal, however, increasing the genetic similarity within the breed often results in the spread of hereditary diseases (Çakmak and Yardibi., 2019). Bovine leukocyte adhesion deficiency syndrome (BLAD) is an autosomal recessive hereditary disease in Holstein–Friesian cattle. The first report was published in 1983 by Hagemoser *et al.* The case of a 1–year old Holstein heifer with fever, diarrhea and marked neutrophilia was referred to as “bovine granulocytopeny syndrome (Gu *et al.*, 2004). Later cases from the 1990s confirmed the similarity to human leukocyte adhesion deficiency (LAD) (Nagahata, 2004) and the syndrome was renamed to BLAD.

The mutation can be traced back to a heterozygous bull called Osborndale Ivanhoé and its offspring (Penstate Ivanhow star – son and Carlin M Ivanhoe Bell – grandson) (Kumar and Sharma, 2009). Due to their high genetic merit for milk production these sires founded one of the main Holstein lineages through artificial insemination (Shuster *et al.*, 1992). International trading of sperm and bulls potentiated the rapid (within several years) and worldwide spread of the problem (Akyuz *et al.*, 2010).

Prevalence

In 1990, the carrier frequency of BLAD was estimated to be 15% among Holstein bulls and 6% among Holstein cows in the United States (Gu *et al.*, 2004) with carrier frequency as high as 23% for AI–sampled bulls (Powell *et al.*, 1996). Data from Japan showed BLAD–carrier prevalence in the range 0 to 23.5% and mean BLAD–carrier prevalence of 8.1% (Nagahata *et al.*, 1997). In Germany the maximum frequency of BLAD reached 24% in 2000 and declined to approximately 1.6% by 2007 (Schütz *et al.*, 2008). Data from Poland shows 7.9% carrier frequency during the period 1995–1997 with decline to 0.8% in 2004–2006 (Czarnik *et al.*, 2007).

Although the gene frequency has been reduced dramatically after the introduction of DNA testing there are still cases published from different countries. After 2000 reports are available from Iran (Norouzy *et al.*, 2005), China (Ma *et al.*, 2006), Turkey (Akyuz and Ertugrul, 2006; Meydan *et al.*, 2010; Çakmak and Yardibi, 2019), India (Patel *et al.*, 2007; Roy *et al.*, 2012; Kotikalapudi *et*

al., 2017), Poland (Czarnik *et al.*, 2007), Germany (Schütz *et al.*, 2008), Pakistan (Nasreen *et al.*, 2009), Indonesia (Dagong *et al.*, 2018), Lithuania (Morkuniene *et al.*, 2019).

The incidence of BLAD carriers has been estimated from 0.5% for Lithuania Holstein (Morkuniene *et al.*, 2019) to 1.33% for Turkish (Çakmak and Yardibi, 2019), 1.38% Chinese (Sun *et al.*, 2011) and 1.59 for Indian (Roy *et al.*, 2012) cattle. The percentage of carrier animals is higher in some studies from Iran (3.33%) (Norouzy *et al.*, 2005), India (4%) (Ignetious *et al.*, 2020) and Brazil (5.7%) (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2000).

Etiology

The condition is caused by a point mutation (adenine to guanine) at position 383 of the CD18 gene (Kehrli *et al.*, 1990), located on chromosome 1 (BTA1) (Kumar and Sharma, 2009) which causes an aspartic acid to glycine substitution at amino acid 128 (D128G) in the adhesion molecule CD18 (Nagahata, 2004; Kumar and Sharma, 2009). This results in a configurational changes of the beta-subunit of the glycoprotein which cannot be expressed in association with the alpha-subunit on the surface of leukocytes (Müller *et al.*, 1994). The mutation lies within a highly conserved region in the extracellular domain where at least 125 consecutive amino acids are similar in normal human, canine, bovine, porcine, rat, and murine CD18 (Gu *et al.*, 2004). Another point mutation (cytosine to thymine) at position 775 in the same gene is found to be silent (Shuster *et al.*, 1992). A research by Schütz *et al.* (2008) shows that after the introduction of genetic testing the elimination rate of carriers has reached about 45% per year which suggests that a certain proportion of ancestors (mainly cows) possess an unknown BLAD genotype.

Pathophysiology

Kehrli *et al.* published a sequence of articles investigating the immunological basis of the condition (Kehrli *et al.*, 1990; Kehrli *et al.*, 1992a; Kehrli *et al.*, 1992b). The increased susceptibility to bacterial infections associated with LAD results from the inability of leukocytes (especially neutrophils) to adhere to the blood vessel wall and migrate to sites of infection (Gu *et al.*, 2004). Poor leukocyte chemotaxis causes lack of pus formation and peripheral neutrophilia (Justiz Vaillant and Ahmad, 2022).

The integrin family is involved in a variety of cell-matrix and cell-cell adhesion functions that are crucial for normal host defense mechanisms (Mazzone and Ricevuti, 1995). The heterodimeric beta-2 integrin adhesion molecules are composed of identical beta subunits (CD18) and four different alfa subunits (CD11a to CD11d) as for the designation CD18/CD11 (Pareek and Kaminski, 1996). The CD11 subunits are selectively expressed on distinct populations of leukocytes to mediate a variety of adhesion-related functions and form CD18/ CD11a (leukocyte function-associated antigen 1 (LFA-1), CD18/CD11b (macrophage antigen 1 (Mac-1), CD18/CD11c (p150,95) and CD18/CD11d (α D β 2) (Gu *et al.*, 2004). Expression requires intracellular association of both subunits, therefore defects in CD18 result in disfunction of all beta-2 integrins (Pareek and Kaminski, 1996).

In vitro assessment of neutrophil function and leukocyte integrin expression from a BLAD calf showed decreased expression of leukocyte integrins on the cell surface, decreased ability to aggregate in response to chemotactic stimuli, and decreased ability to migrate across bovine endothelial cell monolayers (Olchowy *et al.*, 1994).

Clinical signs

The condition affects young animals usually between the age of 2 weeks and 15 months (Müller *et al.*, 1994). Most BLAD-affected cattle die without having the diagnosis established, probably before one year of age (Meydan *et al.*, 2013); however, some cows survive for more than two years, but their reproduction and milk performances are poor (Meydan *et al.*, 2010).

Low birthweight and unthriftiness are observed in all species affected by leucocyte adhesion deficiency (LAD) (Gerardi, 1996). Clinical findings include recurrent necrotic and indolent infections of mucous membranes (Nagahata, 2004) due to secondary bacterial or fungal involvement (Gerardi, 1996). BLAD cases may be represented by fever, anorexia, ulcerative gingivitis, severe periodontitis, loss of teeth, ulcerative and granulomatous stomatitis, pneumonia, recurrent or chronic diarrhea, impaired wound healing, failure of suppuration, dermatitis, stunted growth (Nagahata *et al.*, 1993; Müller *et al.*, 1994; Pareek and Kaminski, 1996; Gu *et al.*, 2004; Nagahata, 2004). The outcome is early death which causes great economic loss in Holstein herds. Animals usually do not reach sexual maturity or if they do there can be infertility or abnormalities in the sex cycle (Müller *et al.*, 1994).

Interestingly, a “natural” cord blood transplant was described in dizygotic twins with BLAD; as a result each twin was born with two distinct populations of CD18⁻ and CD18⁺ leukocytes in circulation in approximately equal proportions (Gu *et al.*, 2004).

BLAD syndrome should be kept in mind as a differential diagnosis to common calthood diseases such as pneumonia and diarrhea (Pareek and Kaminski, 1996).

Diagnostics

Laboratory findings are characterized by marked neutrophilia, hypoalbuminemia, hyperglobulinemia and hypoglycemia (Nagahata, 2004). Extreme leukocytosis due to mature neutrophilia and moderate lympho- and monocytosis accompany most cases (Müller *et al.*, 1994). Chronic progressive neutrophilia may reach levels of above > 80,000 cells/ μ l and counts in excess of 200,000 cells/ μ l are not uncommon (Gu *et al.*, 2004).

Cell surface adherence reactions are of central importance in leukocyte functions which contribute to host defenses against infections (Nagahata *et al.*, 1993). The adherence to nylon fibers of neutrophils from affected cases is severely impaired; deficiency of CD18 is associated with profound defects of leukocyte functions (Nagahata *et al.*, 1993). Flow cytometry analysis is able to demonstrate the absence of functional CD18 and the associated alpha subunit molecules on the surface of leukocytes using CD11 and CD18 monoclonal antibodies (Justiz Vaillant and Ahmad, 2022).

Several molecular methods have been developed to detect both homozygous cases as well as heterozygous carriers (Müller *et al.*, 1994). Techniques include PCR – RFLP (Polymerase Chain Reaction – Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism) (Natonek, 2000; Ignietious *et al.*, 2020), PCR–SSCP (Polymerase Chain Reaction – Single Strand Conformation Polymorphism Analysis) (Kumar and Sharma, 2009), real time PCR (Zhang *et al.* 2012) and SNP genotyping based T–ARMS–PCR assay (Tetra primer – Amplification Refractory Mutation System – PCR) (Alyethodi *et al.*, 2016). The mutation at nucleotide 383 eliminates a Taq I restriction site and creates a Hae III site, which allows the identification of normal, carrier and affected animals (Jørgensen *et al.*, 1993; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2000). Commercial testing is available through several institutions like Immgen, Inc., College Station, Tex.; GenMARK, De Forest, Wis.; VITA–TECH Laboratories, Buffalo, N.Y.; US Davis Genetic Laboratory; CLARIFIDE®, Zoetis Genetics; etc.

Molecular methods can help to control the genetic disorders in animal populations (Şahin *et al.*, 2013) and BLAD is a good example of doing so. Test results can be described as normal (not affected), carrier (heterozygous) and affected. Crossing a normal to a BLAD-carrier animal results in no clinical evidence of diseases of their offspring; however half of them will be carriers. Crossing two carrier animals results in a 25% chance of a BLAD-affected calf and a 50% chance of a carrier state.

Sample materials for testing include hair follicles, blood cards, whole blood tubes, tissue samples with Tissue Sampling Unit (TSU) (Allflex®).

Evidence about the association of the BLAD allele to performance traits either through pleiotropy or linkage, is inconclusive (Powell *et al.*, 1996); however, cows that manage to survive are characterized by low production and reproduction performance (Meydan *et al.*, 2010).

Histopathology

Biopsy in BLAD-affected calves shows neutrophils present in numerous congested vessels and the splenic red pulp, but not in ulcerated intestinal mucosa and Peyer's patch areas (Gu *et al.*, 2004). Inflammatory infiltrates are completely devoid of neutrophils and there is no pus formation (Justiz Vaillant and Ahmad, 2022). Bone marrow examination reveals myeloid hyperplasia with increased myeloid-to-erythroid ratio (Gu *et al.*, 2004).

Leukocyte adhesion deficiency in other species

LAD in humans has been divided to three types according to defects in the leukocyte adhesion cascade: LAD type I disease as a result of deficiency of the integrin $\beta 2$ subunit (CD18), LAD type II disease due to absence of the selectin ligand (SleX) and LAD type III disease caused by defects in G protein-coupled receptor-mediated integrin activation (Gu *et al.*, 2004). The initial presentation is usually characterized by infection of the umbilical stump followed by bacterial infection of mucosae (gingivitis and periodontitis) and skin (nonhealing wounds) (Bauer *et al.*, 2004). LAD I patients often present with delayed separation of the umbilical cord, recurrent pyogenic infections within the first weeks of life, infections caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, absent pus formation, periodontitis (Justiz Vaillant and Ahmad, 2022).

The level of neutrophil function abnormalities is directly related to severity of disease with moderate cases expressing 1 to 10% of normal CD11/CD18 levels compared to severe cases with less than 1% of normal CD11/CD18 levels (Gu *et al.*, 2004). Severe LAD-I is frequently fatal before the age of 2 years without allogeneic transplantation (Novoa *et al.*, 2017). However, low levels of beta 2 expression may result in milder clinical signs of recurrent infection and better prognosis (Kuijpers *et al.*, 1997).

LAD I, the most common type, is similar to diseases described in other species. The condition has been found in Irish Setter dogs and crosses from Europe, US and Australia (Debenham *et al.*, 2002; Foureman *et al.*, 2002; Jobling *et al.*, 2003). Canine leukocyte adhesion deficiency (CLAD) is characterized by omphalitis shortly after birth, severe gingivitis, lymphadenopathy, poor wound healing, low body weight, and episodes of infection; despite antibiotic therapy, affected pups die or are euthanized within the first few months of life (Bauer *et al.*, 2004).

An insertion mutation in the murine CD18 gene generated viable hypomorphic individuals that resembled the clinical presentation of mild to moderate LAD (Gu *et al.*, 2004). Later, CD18 null mice were created for demonstrating the role of CD11/CD18 integrins in T cell responses (Scharffetter-Kochanek *et al.*, 1998). Cases with complete deficiency in CD18 developed the signs expected

for severe LAD with chronic dermatitis, neutrophilia, increased immunoglobulin concentrations, lymphadenopathy, splenomegaly and 10 to 40% mortality in the perinatal period (Gu *et al.*, 2004).

Animal cases like CLAD-affected Setters, BLAD homozygous Holstein cattle and CD18 null mice present valuable models for investigation of LAD I disease in humans. Therefore, they should be recognized and studied with attention in order to increase the understanding about this complex syndrome.

Treatment

Patients with LAD need prophylactic and often prolonged antibiotic therapy; surgical debridement of nonhealing wounds is also necessary (Bauer *et al.*, 2004). Hematopoietic stem cell transplantation remains the only curative treatment in humans; however, this approach is limited by transplant-related toxicities and graft-versus-host disease (Bauer and Hickstein, 2000). Gene therapy has been attempted with autologous CD18 gene-corrected stem cells; however, infused hematopoietic stem cells did not possess a selective proliferative advantage and there was no persistence of the CD18 gene marked neutrophils (Bauer *et al.*, 2004). The same regimens have been investigated in BLAD and CLAD cases. Matched related donor bone marrow transplantation has been described in affected dogs and calves (Gu *et al.*, 2004). Therefore animal models possess increased relevance for novel approaches to therapy.

Prevention

About 300 hereditary diseases have been detected in cattle breeds during the last fifty years and a number of them have spread rapidly in the population (Çakmak and Yardibi, 2019). Intense selection of bulls based upon lactational performance of their daughters and the use of artificial insemination has led to the widespread of autosomal recessive disorders like BLAD (Shuster *et al.*, 1992). The problem with this group of heritable diseases is that carriers do not show clinical symptoms but are able to transmit the mutated alleles to their offspring (Alyethodi *et al.*, 2016). Fast, reliable and inexpensive assays should be developed in order to increase the efficacy of genetic testing for BLAD and other common genetic disorders in cattle. Affected as well as carrier animals should be culled and this non-BLAD program should be maintained at the highest level in the case of bulls used for artificial insemination. Marker-assisted selection is capable of substantially reduce the frequency of a mutation and this was confirmed by decreasing the BLAD allelic frequency in the active sire population from 9.4% in 1997 to 0.3% in 2007 as published by Schütz *et al.* (2008). According to the same authors strict exclusion of all carriers is advantageous to eliminate the mutation; however many important sires or cows might be affected; therefore carrier animals should be excluded from the breeding program as far as possible or mating should be allowed only if no homozygous affected offspring can be expected (e.g., heterozygous sires are crossed only to homozygous wild-type cows). This strategy is going to result in steady decrease in mutated allele frequency without negative productive effects in the progeny.

Conclusion

To the best of our knowledge there is no information about the prevalence of BLAD syndrome in Holstein cattle and crosses from Bulgaria. Having in mind the extensive use of artificial insemination and the relatively high percentage of carriers present despite the introduction of genetic testing, cases of BLAD may be expected, especially if attention is focused on calves with severe and

unexpected health problems. Disorders that lead to negative economic effects should be popularized in order to increase the chance of clinical and laboratory diagnosis as a step in the identification of affected as well as carrier animals.

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